

ANCIENT NEAR EASTERN LAW

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Introduction

Law is a system of rules that a society develops to define and/or deal with social relationships, crimes, or particular types of agreements. Justice could also be defined as the moral principle that guides society in awarding each person what corresponds to his or her legal station in that society. Scholars have traditionally approached the origins and early development of these concepts through the usage of different cuneiform sources from ancient Mesopotamia. This paper hopes to extract an overview of the origins, nature, and historiographical differences of these approaches to Ancient Near Eastern legal systems.

Even if we cannot precisely identify the origin of the first legal system, it can probably be placed in the late period of prehistory, although the only possible point where one can with any certainty recognize a legal structure is after the invention of writing, which took place sometime around the middle of the 4th millennium BC, somewhere in southern Mesopotamia, potentially in Uruk. As the earliest texts show that there were obligations and expectations, thus we must assume that there was something like a conceptual legal structure into which these texts fitted, with an actual written structure perhaps only coming later. Some may contend that legal texts may already have been created by the beginning of 3rd millennium BC.¹ However, it is more realistic to think that legal concepts (as distinct from economic obligations and social responsibilities) may not have been expressed in any explicit form until centuries later.

Regardless, the tradition of Ancient Near Eastern law was gradually codified and expanded from the middle of the third millennium until the last centuries of the 1st millennium BC, so we face a time spectrum of more than 3,000 years when the idea of legal systems began to form in Mesopotamia, and at least two millennia during which legal codes were consciously developed. Most of the known law codes were written in Semitic Akkadian, while the earliest conceptual

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¹ That is, from the Jemdet Nasr Period, c. 3000–2900 BC (cf. Molina 2000, 26); for the earliest texts, see Molina 2000; Wilcke 2003 and 2007; Lafont and Westbrook 2003.

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